

THE AWARENESS, ATTITUDE, AND OPINIONS OF SOCIAL STUDIES TEACHERS REGARDING THE USE OF MOVIES AND SERIALS IN TEACHING HISTORY SUBJECTS

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Abstract:

In formal education, learning content has complete representative characteristics, and the main function of teachers is to be able to present the reality by materializing it through its representations. In this context; communication, the written, visual and oral language creating the communication, and audio-visual education technologies that bring depth and dimension to communication has become the indispensable professional instruments of teachers in this media age that we are a part of. However, due to a series of financial, legal and technical justifications and various prejudices that these justifications feed, it cannot be claimed that audio-visual teaching materials and technologies, particularly movie products, have a widespread and institutionalized area of use worldwide. This research aims to reveal the knowledge and awareness levels of social studies teachers in Turkey on the subjects regarding history teaching, their attitudes for the use of movies and serials, and their negative or positive opinions and recommendations on this issue. Within the frame of this purpose, a general qualified questionnaire form that requires only one answer was applied for the teachers participating in the research as well as semi-structured interviews were made with each teacher individually. The obtained data were coded and interpreted according to categories of research questions, and solutions were offered to overcome the reflected problems and obstacles.

Keywords: history teaching, social studies teaching, history teaching materials, social studies education materials, use of movies and serials in teaching

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1. Introduction

That the students have interest and are motivated in learning has become one of the central subjects of contemporary pedagogy and didactics (Babić, 2014: 18). Because the approaches based on cognitive learning and where the teacher is the center depends on oral and written perception (Benaissa, 2012: 12), and thus, they are neither inadequate to motivate students nor provide permanent learning. The requirement to overcome this problem has led pedagogues and teachers search for new methods and materials, and in recent years, teaching materials, particularly with audio-visual property, started to be designed, and activities based on the use of such materials started to be planned. Audio-visual materials can be both regarded as teaching materials and a teaching method that is based on audio-visual sensitivity of the learners (Babić, 2014: 5; Benaissa, 2012: 16).

The primary audio-visual material sources are the low cost printed visuals as well as media tools i.e. TV, the Internet, and movies, which influence the children's out-of-school life. Arcan, Bruening, & Story (2013: 1) detected that only the time that children and youngsters spend in front of the TV was 4.5 hours a day. When the other media tools are added to that as well, this period reaches approximately 7 hours a day and 50 hours a week (Russell III, 2012: 1, 157). In the unlimited communication pattern which is also known as Médiacratie (Kaboré, 2007: 4), considering the possible adverse effects of information techniques such as fictionality, ideological propositions, disinformation and manipulation which lead to social engineering through media sources, the use of media tools in teaching becomes important also in terms of literacy education. It is a determining variable that the children forming the future's raw material become individuals "*who have gained visual literacy skills, can analyze audio-visual codes and think critically*" (Kaboré, 2007: 7) to be able to build a transparent and predictable society which is dedicated to reality and close to manipulation. Here in this regard, starting visual experiences at early age and enriching the learning processes from a visual perspective is not only a teaching strategy for making education interesting and motivating, but also an approach for visual cultural education that positively affects the visual literacy and visual communication skills of children in their future lives (Fransecky & Debes, 1972: 23).

Another important aspect of using audio-visual materials in teaching is to involve children in a world of representation and function as a source that enriches their world of fantasy and thought. Whether it is a map, a visual or audio file, all media products consist of representations of reality (Zberg, 2013: 3). Each of them has been fictionalized by its creator. Furthermore, since the spectators also watch with eyes representing different living experiences and see different things, each media product is recreated with the imaginations of people using them (Zberg, 2013: 5).

Among audio-visual materials, the movies have a special place and certain superiorities which cannot be performed by other materials. First of all, the cinema which the movie is produced is regarded as the most influential type of art developed since the literature has emerged (Nourrisson, 2014: 2; Wegner, 1977: 6). Its influence

arises from being a synthesis of multiple arts and depending on an elasticity which internalizes all features of preceding arts within its own rules rather than being an independent branch of art (Özön, 1985: 12-13). Besides, cinema is not only a synthesis of arts but rather a communication tool bringing all other arts to large masses (Özön, 2008: 9-10) as well as a language of expression and statement which makes it acknowledged as a type of literature (Wegner, 1977: 7). Whether defined as a field of art or literature and/or a media, it is obvious that *"film is the most influential and seductive force have" available to us to teach, to convince, and to transmit ideas and information - or simply to show the world as it is*" as Wegner (1977: 8) states.

The movies which are the fundamental product of the art of cinema are divided into quite different categories technically according to their techniques, whether being fictional or not, budgets, periods, lengths, being color or black-white, silent or talking, one dimensional or three dimensional. Again, there are classifications made according to target market i.e. audience of the film considering criteria such as age, gender, and family. However, since a movie mostly has features that could be included in more than one category; categories which are usually based on scenario i.e. subject are preferred in databases that promote, list, point and rate the movies. In such basic classification approaches, the one which could be applicable for teachers is no doubt the classifications referring the audience first (Kelly, M., 2018, September 28). All the G-Rated movies are potential teaching materials for teachers. However, it should be kept in mind that this superficial classification is functional only for a pre-classification. What the teacher has to focus on making the right choice is whether the movies he/she reviewed are *"suitable to learning targets, the content and messages are compatible with intellectual and emotional features of children and contain technical details to be observed and examined"* (Bathurst, 1941: 3; La Commission Nationale Française pour l'UNESCO, 2018). Apart from those, despite not being a criterion to choose a movie, there are also movies which are recommended to consider during the choosing process in terms of their certain characteristics. For example, Matz & Pingatore (2005: 190) state that the most effective movies in terms of teaching are the ones shot during the period about which the scenarios treated because such films showed a higher level of truth compared to movies made in the following years and that the teachers could access such kind of movies most of which has become a public property at the databases such as www.archive.org and <http://www.tcm.turner.com>.

Defaye & Defaye (2018) recommend teachers to consider especially the silent and short-length movies during movie choosing; because they assert that silent movies direct children to vocalization, analyze the role of music and sound effects in staging a movie and allow them to question the effect of sounds on emotions. They explain the reason to recommend short-length movies with the thought that the movies should be watched as an active audience by avoiding a consumer sense and as the short-length movies better meet this requirement keeping children's attention and curiosity.

That visual literacy becoming a current education topic has also carried the use of movies as a unique audio-visual material in teaching as being one of the recent issues remaining on the agenda continuously. For example, The National Council of Teachers

of English, and The International Reading Association have defined being a critical and creative user of movies and television as one of the components of being literate in the modern society in a joint declaration they made in 1996 (Considine & Baker, 2006: 12). Furthermore, some international institutions such as The International Educational Cinematographic Institute (IECI) were established under the roof of The European Educational Film Congress and UN in order to create a database for stakeholder organizations so as to evaluate, classify and archive education movies (Fuchs, Bruch, & Annegarn-Gläß, 2016: 2). Following the intensive works conducted, movies were acknowledged at least as an indisputable supportive, and complementary materials in teaching (Nourrisson, 2014: 1; Wagnon & André, 2014: 10), many analyses and research findings were obtained on the movie using in teaching provides certain benefits. The most said benefits among those can be listed as follows (Babić, 2014: 4, 18-20, 32; Bettina, 2001: 2; Crockett, 2018: 4; Culture et Démocratie Asbl.: 5-8; Çakmakçı, 2017: 9; Defaye & Defaye, 2018; Fuchs, Bruch, & Annegarn-Gläß, 2016: 1; Wegner, 1977: 8, 26):

- *Being interesting*: Bringing the best educators, scientists, and poets to classroom, the movies enrich school life and make applicable student-centered education and cooperative learning.
- *To facilitate learning*: They simplify the knowledge, equalize the knowledge as different from written texts for the audience, and encourage class participation.
- *Individualization of teaching*: The movies address different styles of learning, diversify the presentation of knowledge; for example, while helping students with a low level of abstraction in learning, they also contribute for children with inadequate speaking and writing skills to develop their vocabulary and writing skills.
- *Communication skills*: The films improve the communication between teachers and students as well as between classmates and groups; they bring the skill of living together by creating common references.
- *Critical thinking*: The movies provide critical observation, create a rich infrastructure for oral discussion, and make external reality interpretable.
- *Affective learning*: The sense of appreciation for the concepts subject to movie increases in students, interest, and curiosity arouse, appropriate and realistic images form.
- *Multiculturalism*: The films increase cultural awareness regarding the other lifestyles, emphasize the richness of cultural diversity, encourage intercultural identity consciousness, and intercultural dialogue.
- *Aesthetic development*: The movies encourage artistic sensitivity and form joy and pleasure.

Despite all these contributions and benefits; Fuchs, Bruch, and Annegarn-Gläß (2016: 9-10) assert that it has been late worldwide to include new technologies as teaching materials in school or teaching programs. When all current technologies are considered, there are a lot of reasons for this delay in financial, political, and administrative aspects. In the context of the movie using in teaching, however, it is understood that this delay generally arises from a structural dispute between the nature

of films and the educational environment. To point out some basic prominent issues in this subject will form a meaningful frame also in terms of understanding the opinions of teachers who participated at this study (Donnelly, 2014: 23-25; Kelly, 2018, September 28; Metzger, 2017: 3-4; Poirier, 1995, 18-19; Russell III W., 2012: 7, 10; Sasseville and Marquis, 2015: 16-19):

- *Time incompatibility problem:* Movies are not teaching materials alone. They are technological products on which the teacher should make preview, sort out the sections to be watched, design activities about those sections, prepare physical conditions suitable to watch, and should definitely be used in plan. Thus, they require too much time both for their preparation stage before watching or while watching in class.
- *Value and morality problem:* The movies are not designed specifically to be teaching materials. Therefore, they don't have a suitable educational language for learning outcomes like in textbooks. In terms of social reality representation; the use of vulgarization, jargon, and slang is usual for movie language. However, this might be an obstacle which is not deemed pleasant by families according to the movie's characteristics, and the use of some films in teaching might require receiving permission of families and school administration.
- *The problem of teacher adequacy:* Although it is observable that teachers attach special importance to the use of movies, many studies conducted not only in Turkey but also in different countries demonstrate that teachers don't have enough level of knowledge and skill on how to do it, and that many of them fail to properly carry out certain preliminary preparations, which are deemed to be the key to use movies.
- *The problem to find suitable material:* As we also stated above, the movie products are not produced by specifically considering the necessities of educational institutions. Thus, it is almost impossible to find a movie which is included in a suitable category for the family and general viewers as well as one fit for learning purposes as a whole. As a matter of course, this obliges a quite laborious preliminary study for reviewing the potentially suitable movies very carefully and sorting out their certain parts.

Despite all these obstacles and problems, teachers put emphasis on the movie using and try to make use of them in their classes as much as possible. For example, a research made on social studies teachers revealed that all teachers participating in the study used movies at least once a month (Russel III, 2012: 157). Nevertheless, due to current issues, this is, of course, a way of use that the movies are used as a textbook, mostly preferred only for their contents and limited by "*reading, watching and replying some questions*" (Benaissa, 2012: 19; Russell III W., 2012: 10).

2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework: Use of Movies and Serials in Teaching History

The use of movie and serials has a specific place and importance particularly in teaching history. Because a time frame in the past, states or countries which no longer exist, changed boundaries, disappeared or modified cultures, characters who do not live anymore, abolished rules, collective memory of a period which is even impossible to recall make history teaching a bunch of imaginary and fictional narrations which are even beyond the abstract for students. On the other side, affective learning has now gained great importance along with cognitive outcomes in today's education approaches; as a result of that, historical consciousness, historian's view, attitudes and values for history reading have become basic requirements in teaching history. For this purpose, it is necessary to create teaching environments which address different sense organs of students and are rich in terms of teaching technologies (Demircioğlu, 2007: 78). Among these technologies, there are specific contributions and benefits of movies that facilitate learning of abstract historical subjects. The films (Buchanan, 2012: 21-22; Donnelly, 2014: 19; O'Connor, 1987: 7, 43; Reynaud, 2008: 52; Russell III, 2012: 157, 10; Sasseville and Marquis, 2015: 3-4, 8; Zberg, 2013: 8):

- visualize the discussed period, make it more concrete and vivid;
- make the students closer to people and events during the discussed period, strengthen their empathies;
- activate imagination by representing the history;
- bring an historical point of view and historical thought concepts;
- reveal the disputed and controversial issues of the past;
- enable learning by having fun, or having fun by learning;
- offer alternative perspectives and counter stories containing untold details about the known events;
- constitute sample on how the evidences are used for various facts, circumstances, and realities;
- improve visual literacy skills.

Despite all these contributions and benefits, there are also opinions referring to the negative aspects of movie and serial using in history teaching. Let us explain these briefly in categories (Briand, 2014: 10; Donnelly, 2014: 17-18; Kelly, 2018, September 28; Metzger, 2017: 3-4; Özön, 2008: 9-10; Reynaud, 2008: 48; Sasseville and Marquis, 2015: 2):

- *The problem of fictionality of movies:* The movies may twist historical affects, be produced as a propaganda instrument, and serve for today's benefits from various aspects and deform values and attitudes of the past in acting that reflects them with today's language.
- *Distracting effect of movies:* In the applications where students are degraded to a passive audience, the films may create a distracting effect like the Internet, computers, and other technologies.

- *The problem of teacher adequacy:* Teachers are not equipped enough to teach history lesson by making use of movies and serials.
- *The environment and condition problem:* The nature of the art of cinema requires specific watching conditions. Going to a movie theater and watching a whole movie may be a waste of time, most of which may not fit with teaching purposes. However, taking certain sections of a film and using them at a class environment and on a screen also are not compatible with the nature of the movie.

Teachers who appreciate using movie and serial in history teaching prefer to use documentaries whose primary purpose is to present document and proof, wish to show reality and the variable, is focused on teaching, is against fiction and requires a certain intellectual effort for its audiences (Benaissa, 2012: 20-22; Öztaş, 2007: 34; Zberg, 2013: 5) in order to go beyond such negative point of view. When it comes to closeness to reality and truth, the documentaries should be naturally preferred first compared to movies. However, the primary purpose of using movie and serial in history teaching is not to present cinematic evidences that reflect only the reality and truth, and the opinions finding movies and serials negative also do not reflect the absolute truth anyway.

Namely, the fictionality in movies is also applicable for the history science itself as well. Because what the historians can do is not recording the past but is limited to offering an insight into it; moreover, they do it under the frame, language and concerns of today from which they cannot isolate themselves (Reynaud, 2008: 48). That's why many worldwide subjective and fictional historiographical studies that have entered into reader's world and even more biased textbooks make suspicious the judgment that a historian is always more objective than a scenarist or film director. Moreover, the movies should not be solely watched for the historical period they show as they cannot be merely regarded as historical document, instead; they should be acknowledged as artistic products and should be watched for what they say about the values of society that they address as well as their cinema elements, historicalness, language, and aesthetics (Benaissa, 2012: 19; Meyniac, 2002; Reynaud, 2008: 51).

Distraction of movies is a problem based on school epistemology and can be solved by working on it. Because in movie and serial using, the answers to basic questions such as "when, how, how much, where" have not become internalized in teachers' world as an education method and material using subject (Héry-Vielpeau, 2018).

When it comes to teacher adequacy issue, movies and serials are not the only subjects to discuss here. Teachers have adequacy problems in many other areas and have solution expectations, and this is not the problem of the movie sector, but the policy and process for teacher training.

Finally, the environment and condition problem is again an issue related to technical infrastructure and physical properties of schools, and sources of finance allocated for this; thus, its source is not the movies and serials. Moreover, the key point of teaching with films and serials is not the movie itself or the action of movie watching, but using certain aspects of the movie as an activity instrument (Metzger, 2017: 5). For that, it is much more useful to watch short sections from movies and study on certain

elements (Considine & Baker, 2006: 14). In addition, since the movies can be used by being coded to different learning purposes such as “*a visual textbook, description of atmosphere, analogy, historiography sapling, and springboard*” (Russell III, 2012: 158), it is necessary not to consider film sections which have been converted to teaching materials as a cinema product which is screened in theaters.

3. Material and Methods

The main purpose of this study is to determine the awareness, attitudes, and opinions of social studies teachers and the conditions and reasons they had asserted for their ground regarding the use of movies and serials in teaching history subjects. For this purpose, the following research questions were searched for an answer in three different categories:

- The category of knowledge and awareness regarding historical movies and serials and history teaching
- The category of attitudes regarding historical movies and serials and history teaching
- The category of opinions regarding historical movies and serials and history teaching

The research was conducted according to phenomenology design, and descriptive analysis was made by making use of qualitative research methodology. A questionnaire form was used in order to obtain factual data on teachers' professional knowledge and experiences in using movies and serials, and data were collected using a semi-structured interview technique as part of phenomenology design. Both the questionnaire with “The use of Historical Movies and Serials in History Education” title and the same-titled Semi-Structured Interview Form containing open and close end questions were prepared based on relevant literature and research questions by researchers. The prepared questionnaire form and interview questions were first submitted to examination and opinions of 4 expert academicians of the field, following that, views of 2 social studies teachers were taken in company with pilot interview and practices after the necessary corrections were done. The questionnaire and semi-structured interview questions were applied to 23 social studies teachers working at 6 secondary schools representing lower, middle, and upper- income groups in Bursa province. The data obtained from the questionnaire and interviews were organized and interpreted according to categories of pre-designed research questions.

4. Findings and Interpretations

a) Questionnaire Form Findings

Table 1: Do you think there are enough cinema products suitable for the level of students in order to be used for units and subjects related to history education?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	No (T1 - T23)	23
2	Yes	0

(*T: Coded teacher)

Table 2: If you make use of cinema products at your lessons, how many activities do you organize based on movies and serials in one academic year?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	2 activities (T3, T4, T5, T8, T10, T12, T14, T20, T22, T23)	10
2	1 activity (T7, T9, T11, T13, T16, T21)	6
3	I don't benefit it (T6, T15, T17)	3
4	4 activities (T18, T19)	2
5	3 activities (T2)	1
6	More than 4 activities (T1)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was detected that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, and 4 while male teachers had in items 1, 2, and 3. When compared to their length of service, it was determined that teachers having 1-9 years of seniority had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, and 3 while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority had in items 1 and 2, and teachers having 20 years or more seniority in items 1 and 4.

Table 3: Are there enough sources of cinema products which were categorized and archived by the Ministry of Education, private institutions and volunteers, and then presented to teachers' access?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	No (T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12, T13, T14, T15, T17, T18, T19, T20, T21, T22, T23)	22
2	Yes (T16)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was found that male and female teachers had an equal frequency in item 1. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that one of the teachers with 1-9 years of seniority had a higher rate 2, and all the other teachers in item 1.

Table 4: Do you think that the teaching education you had received during your undergraduate years brought you suitable and satisfactory professional knowledge and skills to make use of historical movies and serials at your classes?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	Partially enough (T1, T2, T5, T6, T8, T10, T12, T17, T18, T19, T20, T21, T23)	13
2	Not enough (T3, T9, T11, T13, T14, T15, T16, T22)	8
3	Enough (T7)	1
4	No answer (T4)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was detected that male and female teachers had an equal frequency in items 1 and 2. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years of seniority and teachers with 10-19 years of seniority had a higher frequency in items 1 and 2, and teachers with seniority 20 years and above had a higher rate in items 1 and 4.

Table 5: Has there been inservice training practices you participated in contemporary teaching methods and/or teaching materials that contribute you to make use of historical movies and serials?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	No (T1, T2, T3, T4, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12, T13, T14, T15, T16, T17, T18, T19, T20, T22, T23)	21
2	Yes (T5, T21)	2

(*T: Coded teacher)

The majority of male and female teachers have a higher frequency in item 1. When the terms of duty were compared, all the teachers preferred item 1 as a response.

Table 6: Do you think that historical movies and serials concretize the learning content and make learning more accessible?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	Yes (T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T12, T13, T14, T15, T16, T17, T18, T19, T20, T21, T22, T23)	22
2	No (T11)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

Regardless of gender and years of seniority, all teachers, except one, preferred item 1 as the answer.

Table 7: Do you think that making use of historical movies and serials make a positive difference in materializing the outcomes?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	makes a significant positive difference (T1, T2, T4, T5, T6, T7, T9, T10, T12, T13, T14, T15, T16, T17, T18, T19, T20, T21, T23)	19
2	makes a low positive difference (T3, T8, T11, T22)	4
3	does not make any positive difference	0

(*T: Coded teacher)

Regardless of gender and seniority year, almost all teachers preferred item 1 in response.

Table 8: What do you think is the way to watch historical movies and serials as teaching material to make them more useful?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	It is enough to watch certain sequences of the movies by matching them with related subjects and learning outcome (watching oriented events) (T2, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T11, T13, T20, T21, T22)	11
2	Movies or series should be watched completely (watching chronologically) (T1, T3, T4, T10, T14)	5
3	Specific predefined themes of the films should be watched (watching oriented imaginations) (T12, T15, T17, T23)	4
4	Only epic scenes of the films should be watched to develop a sense of appreciation and empathy (watching affectively) (T16, T18, T19)	3

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was detected that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, and 4 while male teachers had in items 1 and 3. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher frequency in items 1, 3, and 4 while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority had in items 1, 2, and 3, and teachers having 20 years and above in items 1 and 4.

Table 9: Please prioritize the following problems that make historical movies and serials difficult to benefit from

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	Lack of movies suitable for pupils levels (T3, T10, T12, T13, T16, T17, T20, T23)	8
2	Lack of accessible cinema resources (T2, T3, T4, T14, T16, T17, T20, T21)	8
3	Lack of films suitable for units and subjects (T3, T11, T13, T17, T18, T21, T22)	7
4	Taking a long time of necessary preparatory works (T6, T7, T9, T10, T20)	5
5	Cost of activities (T16, T17, T20, T21)	4
6	Cognitive and artistic competences of teachers (T1, T4, T6, T7, T8, T10, T21)	7
7	Teachers' skills in using instructional material (T3, T4, T7, T16, T19, T20)	6
8	Too much activity time (T3, T6, T10, T13, T22)	5

(*T: Coded teacher)

In terms of the most important problem, it was found that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 2 and 3, and male teachers in item 1, whereas in terms of the least important problem, female teachers had a higher frequency in item 8. When the terms of duty are compared, it is seen that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher rate in articles 1, 4, and 6; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, and 3; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 3, 6, and 7.

Table 10: In which part of the lessons do you think that using historical movies and serials can be more effective and useful?

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	Development phase (T1, T2, T3, T6, T8, T9, T11, T12, T13, T15, T17, T18, T19, T21, T22, T23)	16
2	Evaluation phase (T4, T7, T14, T16)	4
3	Introduction phase (T5, T10, T20)	3

(*T: Coded teacher)

Female teachers have a higher frequency in items 1 and 2, while male teachers in 1 and 3. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with seniority of 1-9 years and teachers with seniority of 20 years and above had a higher frequency in items 1 and 3, and teachers with seniority of 10-19 years had a higher rate in items 1 and 2.

Based on these numerical data, the following detections can be made on professional knowledge and experiences of teachers which they shared for using historical movies and serials:

- All the teachers think that there are not enough cinema products suitable for the level of students in order to be used in units and subjects related to history.
- Majority of teachers make use of movies and serials, the frequency of this utilization occurs 1 or 2 times in one academic year. While the choice "I don't make use of it" shows high rate in male teachers, the choice "4 activity in a year" shows high frequency in female teachers.
- Except one teacher, all the teachers state that there are not enough sources of cinema products that were categorized and archived by the public or private sector and submitted to teachers' access.
- Majority of teachers express that their undergraduate educations were either partially or not enough at all in bringing suitable and sufficient knowledge and skills for making use of movies and serials.
- Except two teachers, all the other teachers state that they received no inservice training that would contribute them to make use of movies and serials.
- Despite various problems and challenges, teachers mostly think that movies and serials concretize the learning content and make learning easy and that they make a positive difference in the realization of learning outcomes.
- As the technique to make use of movies and serials, most teachers find more suitable to use certain sections of works by matching them with outcomes.
- In the eyes of teachers, the inadequacy of works suitable to the level of students and deficiencies in accessible sources of cinema are remarkable as being the most important problems that make difficult to benefit from movies and serials.
- The problem that the activities based on movies and serials take much time was only told by female teachers with high frequency while that the use of film and serial requires a certain cognitive and artistic background in teachers showed high rate in teachers having 1-9 and 20 or more years of seniority.

- Majority of teachers stated that using movies and serials were more effective and useful in development parts of lessons instead of using in introduction or evaluation parts.

b) Semi-Structured Interview Findings

Table 11: Information on Teachers Included in the Working Group

Variables n= 23		f
Undergraduate Diploma field	Social Studies	22
	Others	1
Gender	Male	11
	Woman	12
Seniority	1-9	11
	10-19	8
	20 and more	4

b.1. Findings in Knowledge and Awareness Category

Table 12: Elements which get the most interest arouse curiosity
in historical films and serials

I.N.	Coded items	f
1	Level of compatibility with historical scientific facts (T2, T3, T4, T5, T7, T10, T12, T18, T19, T22)	10
2	Historical space and historical texture (T1, T8, T11, T15, T16, T17, T20, T21, T23)	9
3	Level of compatibility with the cultural characteristics on which it dwells (T6, T9, T11, T17, T21, T23)	6
4	Ability to reflect the historical period that it's about (T2, T6, T7, T19, T21)	5
5	Characters in movies and series (T16, T17, T18)	3
6	Relevance of cinematographic details (T12, T22)	2
7	Level of information (T14)	1
8	Irrelevant answer (T13)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

In terms of gender, female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 4, and 3, while male teachers had a higher frequency in items 2, 3, and 5. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had higher frequency in items 2, 3, 5, and 6; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, 4, and 7; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 1 and 8.

Table 13: The subjects which are suitable to teach using historical movies and serials

I.N.	Coded 5 th -grade subjects	f
1	Ancient Civilizations (T3, T16, T21)	3
	Coded 6 th -grade subjects	
1	Science, Technology, and Society (T11)	1
2	The Adventure of Democracy (T5)	1
3	Muhammad's Life (T8)	1
4	Turks on the Silk Road (T5)	1
5	All units (T1)	1

Coded 7 th -grade subjects		
1	Establishment and Development of the Ottoman Empire (T9, T15, T16, T18)	4
2	Events in Europe between the 15th and 19th centuries (T7, T8, T11)	3
3	World War I (T8, T10, T12)	3
4	Culture and Heritage (T3, T5, T17)	3
5	Communication (T9, T11)	2
6	Global Connections (T5, T10)	2
7	Crusades (T8)	1
8	Conquest of Istanbul (T20)	1
Coded 8 th -grade subjects		
1	Issues related to Kemalism (T1, T3, T8, T11, T17, T19, T22, T23)	8
2	Independence War (T2, T3, T9, T11, T20, T23)	6
3	All topics (T4, T6, T13, T14)	4
4	National Struggle Period (T5, T17, T23)	3
5	Battle of Çanakkale (T2, T3)	2
6	Mustafa Kemal Atatürk's Life (T2, T8)	2

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was detected that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 3, and 5 of the 8th classes; item 1 of the 5th classes, and item 2 of the 7th classes; while male teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2 and 4 of the 8th classes; items 1, 3, and 4 of the 7th classes. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher frequency in items 1 and 3 of the 7th classes, item 1 of the 5th classes, and 1 and 3 of the 8th classes; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, 4, and 5 of the 8th classes, and item 4 of 7th classes; and teachers having 20 years and above in item 1 of the 8th classes.

Table 14: Suitability criteria for historical movies or serials to be used in lessons

I.N.	Coded criteria	f
1	Accordance with gains (T2, T4, T6, T8, T9, T10, T11, T13, T15, T16, T20, T21, T23)	13
2	Accordance with student level (T2, T3, T6, T12, T13, T17, T18, T20, T22, T23)	10
3	Accordance with historical facts and objectivity (T5, T6, T12, T17, T19, T21)	6
4	Accordance with moral values (T5, T13, T16, T23)	4
5	Accordance with course periods (T5, T7)	2
6	Relevance of cinematic details such as movie set and costume (T2, T17)	2
7	Attracting students' attention (T15, T21)	2
8	Purpose of the scenario (T3, T22)	2
9	Documentary quality (T4)	1
10	Capacity to revive a certain period (T1)	1
11	Irrelevant answer (T14)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 3, and 8; while male teachers in items 1, 2, 3, and 4. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 3, and 7; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, 4, and 6; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 1 and 3.

Table 15: Costume drama according to teachers

I.N.	Coded definitions	f
1	Film that reflects objectively a period in accordance with its own circumstances and facts (T3, T7, T11, T15, T16, T19, T21, T22)	8
2	Generalized answer (T6, T10, T12, T13, T14, T18)	6
3	Film that expresses the texture of a period (T1, T8, T9, T17)	4
4	Film that is about a historical event and reflects the age, environment, and people of this event (T23)	1
5	Film that deals with different dimensions of any period (T20)	1
6	Film that brings by concretizing the past and historical elements to the present (T4)	1
7	Film that exposes esthetically the history (T2)	1
8	Film that shows the aspects of the past that are of interest to the present or that shed light on the future (T5)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was detected that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 6, and 7; while male teachers in other items. When the terms of duty were compared, it was determined that teachers with 1-9 and 10-19 years seniority had a higher rate in items 1, 2, and 3; while teachers having 20 years and above in items 1, 6 and 8.

Based on these numerical data, the following detections can be made on professional knowledge and experience levels of teachers in using historical movies and serials:

- In historical movies and serials, teachers are mostly interested in suitability of the work to historical facts and spaces and textures used in the works.
- The level that the works reflect the period they are about is a high-frequency criterion for both male and female teachers.
- In general, while the 7th and 8th-grade subjects are accepted more suitable for using historical movies and serials, subjects of the 6th grade are accepted at a low level, and among the 5th-grade subjects, only The Ancient Civilizations are considered to be suitable for using historical movies and serials.
- The male and female teachers agree with high frequency in the suitability of Kemalism and the War of Independence subjects for using in historical movies and serials.
- In terms of seniority, it is understood that the teachers having a seniority of 20 years or more find using historical movies and serials only in the 8th grade and as part of subjects related to Kemalism.
- Suitability to learning outcomes, to the student's level and to historical facts form the main criteria that the teachers state with high frequency in terms of using historical movies and serials in lesson. In terms of this criterion, no significant difference was observed in the context of gender and seniority of teachers.
- While female teachers gave general answers for the costume drama concept specifying to stage a certain period in an impartial, concrete and aesthetic way, male teachers explained the same concept by more detailed answers such as a historical texture of a certain period, variables influencing the period, the incident and its characters etc.

- Likewise, if we look from the point of seniority, it is understood that the teachers having 20 years or more seniority seek for features toward concretization of a certain period and establishing a past-present relationship.

b.2. Findings in Attitude Category

Table 16: Attitudes of teachers towards the utilization of historical movies and serials as a teaching material

I.N.	Coded positive attitudes	f
1	concretize soft data (T1, T2, T6, T7, T8, T10, T11, T15, T16, T20, T22)	11
2	increase interest and attention to the lesson (T1, T2, T9, T12, T17, T22, T23)	7
3	General answers (“I find generally positive”) (T3, T4, T13, T14, T21)	5
4	motivate students (T1, T17, T23)	3
5	provide saving on time (T2, T9, T23)	3
6	contribute to the permanence of learning by addressing more sense organs (T6, T19)	2
7	reinforce the learned knowledge (T5, T18)	2
Coded negative attitudes		
1	Duration of the courses is not sufficient to benefit from movies or series (T3, T4, T6, T7, T11, T15, T21, T22)	8
2	It is difficult to find suitable films or series for the curriculum (T3, T11, T16, T17, T18, T19, T23)	7
3	may lead to deviations from the learning objectives (T1, T8, T17, T20)	4
4	may cause the students to become bored or decrease their attention as long as the duration of the activity increases (T9, T10, T13)	3
5	The lack of an appropriate environment and equipment in schools creates technical problems (T6, T7)	2
6	requires a long preparation process for teachers (T2, T7)	2
7	take a long time (T1, T10)	2
Coded uncertain attitudes		
1	No answer (Ö5, Ö12, Ö14)	3

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had higher frequency in items 1, 3 and 6 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1, 2, 5 and 6 of the coded negative attitudes; while male teachers in items 1, 2 and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 2, 3 and 4 of the coded negative attitudes. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had higher frequency in items 1 and 2 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1 and 4 of the coded negative attitudes; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 2, 3 and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 2 and 6 of the coded negative attitudes; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 6 and 7 of the coded positive attitudes, and 1 and 2 of the coded negative attitudes.

Table 17: Attitudes of teachers towards the utilization of historical movies and serials as a teaching method

I.N.	Coded positive attitudes	f
1	contribute to the permanence of learning by addressing more sense organs (T2, T6, T15, T19, T20, T22)	6
2	make the course enjoyable (T1, T5, T17)	3
3	General answers (“I find generally positive”) (T4, T7, T13)	3
4	concretize soft data (T5, T16, T18)	3
5	contribute to affective learning (T1)	1
6	increase motivation (T1)	1
7	facilitate understanding of cause-effect relationships (T20)	1
8	facilitate learning and teaching (T9)	1
Coded negative attitudes		
1	It is more appropriate to use them as materials that support teaching methods (T2, T3, T8, T10, T11, T12, T21, T23)	8
2	Duration of the courses is not sufficient to benefit from movies or series (T6, T19, T22, T23)	4
3	It is difficult to find suitable films or series for the learning objectives (T1, T6, T9, T10)	4
4	Films and series cannot be used as teaching methods (T3, T5, T14)	3
5	may cause the students to become bored or decrease their attention as long as the duration of the activity increases (T17, T22)	2
6	Their use as a teaching method cause time loss (T20, T23)	2
7	The use of films and series as a method is only suitable for some subjects (T15)	1
8	It is difficult to find films or series that are appropriate for the age and level of the pupils (T6)	1
Coded uncertain attitudes		
1	No answer (T2, T4, T7, T8, T11, T12, T13, T16, T18)	9

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 3, and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1, 2, 3, and 4 of the coded negative attitudes; while male teachers in items 1, 2, and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1, 3, and 6 of the coded negative attitudes. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher rate in items 1 and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1, 2, and 3 of the coded negative attitudes; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, and 3 of the coded positive attitudes, and items 1 and 4 of the coded negative attitudes; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 3 and 4 of the coded positive attitudes, and 2 and 4 of the coded negative attitudes.

Table 18: Attitudes of teachers towards the frame of social studies teaching program on historical movies and serials

I.N.	Coded positive attitudes	f
1	The current curriculum is suitable for the use of historical films and series (T1, T3, T4, T5, T8, T10, T11, T12, T13, T14, T16, T20, T22, T23)	14
2	The current curriculum is only suitable for documentary productions (T2)	1
Coded negative attitudes		
1	The current curriculum is not suitable for the use of historical films and series (T9, T15, T17, T18, T19, T21)	6
Coded uncertain attitudes		
1	Irrelevant answer (T6, T7)	2

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1 and 2 of the coded positive attitudes, and item 1 of the coded negative attitudes; while male teachers in item 1 of the coded positive attitudes, and item 1 of the coded negative attitudes. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that all teachers, regardless of seniority, had a higher rate in item 1 of both coded positive and negative attitudes. Based on these numerical data, the following detections can be made on the attitudes of teachers towards making use of historical movies and serials:

- Historical movies and serials are accepted as a positive material by teachers in the context of concretizing the subjects and drawing the attention and interests of students. In this case, male teachers stated that movies and serials had the function of saving on time, as different from female teachers.
- The problem of finding suitable movies for teaching programs was expressed as negative by teachers in every level of seniority.
- It is remarkable that the expression “in case the use of movies or serials get longer by time, they start to distract interest and attention” was expressed in high frequency only by teachers having 1-9 years of seniority, that “it requires an intense preparation process” was expressed only by teachers having 10-19 years of seniority and that “the duration of lessons are not suitable to use movie and serial” only by teachers having 20 years of or more seniority.
- Teachers think that movies and serials contribute to permanent learning as they address more than one sensual organ, but consider using movies and serials, not as a teaching method but teaching material.
- Majority of teachers find the current social studies curriculum suitable to make use of historical movies and serials.

b.3. Findings in Opinions Category

Table 19: Opinions of teachers regarding the points they pay attention during preparation and activity processes while making use of historical movies or serials

I.N.	Coded opinions	f
1	I pay attention to choose a suitable film for the learning objectives (T1, T3, T4, T5, T10, T16, T19, T20, T21, T22, T23)	11
2	I pay attention to motivation by giving information about the film or series to be watched (T2, T3, T4, T7, T11, T14, T16, T20, T21, T23)	10
3	Irrelevant answer (T6, T8, T9, T12, T13, T15, T17, T18)	8
4	During the activity process, I take care to make verbal explanations by taking a break at the moments when I deem necessary (T1, T5, T7, T11, T14, T22)	6
5	I pay attention to the evaluation of the film or series in the final part of the course (T2, T11, T16, T19, T20, T23)	6
6	I pay attention to watching films or series in development stage after a prologue (T2, T3)	2
7	I pay attention to when the best time to watch the film (T4, T22)	2
8	I do not pay attention to a certain point (T1)	1
9	After the activity, I pay attention to using drama method on the subject (T5)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 4, and 5; while male teachers in items 1, 2, 3 and 5. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher rate in items 1, 2, and 3; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, and 4; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 1, 2, 4 and 5.

Table 20: Solutions of teachers regarding the problems and challenges
 in making use of historical movies and serials

I.N.	Coded suggestions	f
1	It should be ensured that there are environments where films can be watched and materials are kept in schools (T5, T7, T11, T12, T15, T16, T20, T21, T23)	9
2	Sufficient number and variety of films and series should be produced in accordance with student level and scientific facts (T1, T3, T12, T13, T14, T22, T23)	7
3	The Ministry of National Education should produce and / or designate films suitable for watching in class (T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T17)	6
4	Short-length and educational films should be produced in order to watch and complete them in one lesson period (T2, T9, T10, T13, T16)	5
5	In order to watch a film, film watching times must be added to the course hours (T5, T21)	2
6	School administrators and teachers should be provided with in-service training to benefit from films and series in teaching (T11, T23)	2
7	Sufficient number of films and series should be produced according to ethical values (T19)	1
8	Using of films and series should be handled in detail and adequately in related courses of Faculties of Education (T18)	1
9	Internet infrastructure and video portals should be accessible in schools (T7)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was found that female and male teachers had an equal frequency in items 1, 2, 3, and 4. When the terms of duty were compared, it was determined that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher rate in items 1 and 4; while teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 2 and 3; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 1 and 3.

Table 21: According to teachers, in order to make use of historical films and serials;
 the properties that material lists and material using guides to be prepared by
 taking curricula as basis should have

I.N.	Coded properties	f
1	Irrelevant answer (T1, T2, T3, T4, T8, T9, T10, T12, T13, T15, T21, T22)	12
2	In the guides, the time to be watched should be determined by associating the films with the learning objectives (T7, T11, T14, T16, T17, T18)	6
3	Guides should be written in clear and simple language (T5, T6, T20, T23)	4
4	Film checklists should be prepared in the guidelines for post-activity (T17, T23)	2
5	Duration of the films should be stated in the guides (T18)	1
6	Guidelines should include teaching methods to be applied and illustrative examples (T19)	1

(*T: Coded teacher)

It was determined that female teachers had a higher frequency in items 1, 2, 5, and 6; while male teachers in items 1, 3, and 4. When the terms of duty were compared, it was found that teachers with 1-9 years seniority had a higher rate in items 1, 3 and 5; while

teachers having 10-19 years of seniority in items 1, 2, and 4; and teachers having 20 years and above in items 3 and 6.

Based on these numerical data, the following detections can be made on the opinions of teachers for using historical movies and serials:

- While making use of historical movies or serials, teachers most care about choosing movies or serials that are suitable to learning outcomes during preparation and activity processes and making a suitable motivation.
- In order to make use of historical movies and serials more effectively, teachers recommend environments to be created at schools that allow watching movies, to archive required tools thereabouts, and that both cinema industry and Ministry of Education should produce under the category of educational movies.
- In terms of recommendation, as different from the others; teachers having 1-9 years of seniority recommend short length films to be produced.
- It is possible to say that teachers have no certain knowledge or thoughts regarding which knowledge and directions should the sample material using guides that will provide an insight to using movie and serial include.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study revealed conclusions similar to findings of various researches carried out in different countries and times, which we referred to in the introduction part. For example in different researches, when considered in terms of knowledge and awareness, the conclusion was that teachers had certain knowledge about negative or positive effects of movies and serials towards learning and teaching processes but felt inadequate about when, how and with which activities they would make use of movies and serials.

In this case, it is possible to say that we obtained parallel results from social studies teachers who participated in the study.

- Most of the teachers stated that they already make use of movies and serials in their lessons and that they try it minimum 1-2 times in an academic year.
- Teachers gave answers proving that they had a background in the importance and benefits of making use of movies and serials in history teaching, required components or limited factors for using movie and serials.
- Teachers did not give answers which would make think that they used movies and serials by a certain method or technique, defined activities, or suitable evaluation activities.
- Thus, almost all teachers stated that they did not gain knowledge and skills that would allow them to make use of movies and serials during their student years at Faculties of Education, and that they did not get inservice training in their professional lives.

It is possible to say that parallelism with other researches is also applicable for attitudes towards using movies and serials. While referring to other researches, we had mentioned that teachers attached importance to using movies and serials and were in a

positive attitude toward making use of them in their lessons as much as possible.

Attitudes towards using movies and serials of social sciences teachers who participated in this study are also considerably positive.

- Teachers find the current social studies curriculum suitable to make use of historical movies and serials.
- According to teachers movies and serials arouse interest and attention of students, concretize subjects, address more than one sensual organ and therefore provide more permanent learning.
- Teachers conceptualize movies and serials only as teaching material or technology, and state that they don't accept using movies and serials as a kind of special teaching method that can be called "teaching with movies".

Finally, the opinions of teachers on the issue also have many similarities, particularly in terms of obstacles and problems experienced during the use of movies and serials. For example, the problems we coded under "time discrepancy, teacher adequacy and finding suitable material" titles depending on the other research results are considerably applicable for social studies teachers in Turkey, too.

- According to teachers, the most essential problem is the lack of movies suitable for the level of students in order to be used for units and subjects related to history education.
- Teachers stated that there were no sufficient and suitable physical and technological conditions to create cinema environment at schools.
- Teachers state that using movies and serials requires certain cognitive and artistic capabilities in teachers.
- According to teachers, using movies and serials as in short-time sections and especially during development part of the lesson is more productive and useful.
- Teachers think that the success in using movies or serials depend on especially choosing a suitable movie or serial, a serious preliminary preparation, and a high motivation made by the teacher.
- The issue of "fictionality of period drama" mentioned by the teachers who participated researches in different countries was not completely mentioned by this concept. However, the statement "movies' and serials' reflection of historical facts in accordance with scientific facts" mentioned as the first criteria is nothing more than stating the same fictionality concept in a different manner.
- For example, a similar case is also available for the issues which we coded under the title "the problem of value and ethics" mentioned by teachers of the other countries. Teachers who participated in this research did not specify such kind of an issue. However, this is a subject which is not related to ignoring the value and ethics criterion, but control of value and ethics issue. While the local democracy traditions in western societies result in the realization of such a control towards schools rather through social environment and civil initiatives, in Turkey; this issue is more of an administrative and political audit. As a matter of course, it is definitely out of the question using the works at the school environment, which

are coded by relevant audit institutions toward not being suitable for general viewers or children.

Based on these obtained research results, the necessary works can be performed by relevant person and institutions in order to make movies and serials to be used more frequent and more efficient in history teaching within the frame of following recommendations:

- The subjects contained in undergraduate programs of teacher training institutions, particularly the issues with Teaching Technologies and Material Design title, should be updated in terms of the point that contemporary teaching technologies have reached, the academic staff instructing these subjects should be given inservice training with respect to using current technology and materials.
- The Ministry of Education should augment the projects they are already conducting and increase the capacity of the digital library within the frame of web-based services, and support the current curricula with short-length didactic movies and documentaries.
- An online educational public cinema and documentary library should be established with the cooperation of the Ministry of Education and cinema industry.
- The principal success variable in using movies and serials for educational purposes is the teacher. In this regard, the productivity for teachers of the Ministry of Education should be increased not only on films and serials but generally on contemporary teaching technologies through adequate inservice trainings.
- Application guides, lesson plans or worksheets showing the “pre-watching, during watching and post-watching” works of teachers should be produced by academicians studying on the subject or by students preparing master thesis in order to be submitted to the service of teachers and create a source of inspiration.

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